

INCREASING STUDENTS' LISTENING AND SPEAKING SKILLS THROUGH COMPETEND BASED APPROACH

¹Abdukhakimova K., ²Rahmatova M.

¹EL teacher at Samarkand State Institute of Foreign languages

²EL teacher at Academic lyceum of Internal Affairs of Samarkand

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Abstract. *This paper work aims to show some ways to students for increasing listening and speaking skills with the help of competent base approach. Not only tips but also some technics for boosting listening and speaking skills are also given here with acute examples. The date about importance of listening and speaking skills are given first then it is given some information about the importance of competent based approach for learners at higher educational centers.*

Keywords: *listening and speaking, CBA (competent based approach), acquisition, increasing speaking, listening tips, techniques, boosting skills.*

INTRODUCTION

Acquisition of language demands us to increase our listening and speaking skills. The most important thing for improving listening and speaking is considered as practice and learning some techniques and tips. Tuning in aptitudes are inactive dialect abilities, that is why, they are used in order to keep generation of dialect. Local English speakers can appear to conversation exceptionally rapidly to a non-native English individual. The spaces between words are not obvious like they are in composed content, so the sounds jumble up together to create one long ambiguous sentence. It takes a whereas of quiet tuning in hone some time recently a non-native English speaker can observe between diverse sounds which make up person words. This makes a difference the non-native speaker to listen where one word closes and another starts. The spaces between words are regularly not capable of being heard, so you would like to know what to tune in for in arrange to partitioned the sounds of discourse. This comes with hone. So of course, numerous people want it. In any case, at the same level, the specified representatives must be competent and ordinarily familiar in English. We can use an English language as we know that English is a universal dialect. So, wherever we travel, of course we can utilize English for communicating with others. And more often than not, individuals who are familiar with English language will utilize English slang words and abrogate the sentence structure. It happens since ordinarily individuals will feel recognizable and can rapidly discover the reason of the sentence conveyed compared to formal English, firm and continuously pay consideration to sentence structure. And ordinarily when we have a conversation, we continuously pay consideration to the structure, at that point talking English will be exceptionally troublesome to do. And we are going to discover it progressively troublesome to communicate specifically.

In arrange to induce prepared for the exam, you would like to begin practicing active listening on a customary premise. Luckily, various tuning in activities can assist you make strides your aptitudes. For case, you'll tune in to melodies and podcasts in English or observe YouTube recordings and well known TV appears with English subtitles. Be that as it may, these methods are generally illustrations of detached tuning in. On the other hand, in arrange to be able to talk English, you wish to boost your dynamic tuning in abilities, which infers taking an interest in an

English discussion and paying consideration whereas tuning in to the other individual to get it, give input, and reply. Of the four aptitudes of dialect learning, tuning in is commonly respected as the hardest and most challenging. It, in any case, has been neglected with much less time given to its instruction as compared with other dialect abilities, like perusing, composing, and talking. Moreover, most considers concentrate more on the profitable aptitudes of composing and talking (Support, 2000, Nunan, 2002). The center in most dialect classrooms is testing hones and more on tuning in works out than on educating the tuning in abilities. Richards and Renandya (2002) recommend that one anticipated reason behind the approach was that tuning in capacities may conceivably be created in classrooms whereas understudies are uncovered to moment dialect experience amid the address. Nunan (2002) accepts that tuning in is commonly respected as a progressively important dialect expertise that underscores the need of obtaining aptitudes and methodologies pertinent for the understanding of the talked dialect. Agreeing to Gilakjani (2016: 1670) Tuning in ability is exceptionally imperative in outside dialect learning since the key to memorize a dialect is to get dialect input. Tragically, tuning in skill is regularly seen as an inactive aptitude within the classroom, as understudies appear to sit unobtrusively and tune in to discussions. On the other hand, Rost (2001) guarantees that tuning in is a critical implies of learning a modern dialect. It is fundamentally by way of tuning in that dialect learners are presented to an unused dialect, which requires and progresses the securing of their in general moment or remote dialect abilities.

To start with and preeminent, Kurudayioglu (2011) proposes, talking is considered as fundamental and basic in tongue learners' execution, both solely and socially since it may be a device for human communication to associate on each day preface. Other than that, Diyaab et al. (2013) proposed that communicative competence is required in arrange to actuate the lingo dominance rather than the reasonable center on sole dialect instruction. Furthermore, Ellis (2012) states, interaction is the key component in a dialect classroom and learning takes portion when the suggestions and murky centers are talked almost utilizing a collective interaction inside the classroom. Ellis (2012) as well communicated that picking up syntactic and essential competence can be fulfilled by acing the talking inclination. In any case, Wardhaugh (2006) claims that speakers of one dialect tend to have phonetic structure of the lingo normally. Subsequently, we are ready to conclude that by talking and communicating inside the target tongue, able to contribute to the enhancement of other tongue aptitudes that we have. By looking at all the headways being made by grown-up learners in Malaysia can illustrate these clarifications. We select to memorize to talk to start with at that point as it were, we learn to induce it the shapes and show more content. At its center, competency-based instruction or (CBE) is an approach to instruction where understudies advance through learning substance and aptitudes based on acing a characterized and straightforward set of center competencies, instead of the time they've went through in course.

Organizing by competencies empowers teachers to coordinated the instructing of scholastics and center life aptitudes such as collaboration and problem-solving, putting the center on a broader set of results and measuring what understudies have really learned. Characterizing center competencies toward these more thorough learning results, enveloping both scholastic information and life abilities, way better plans understudy with the aptitudes and miens they'll require for postsecondary victory. We know that tall school understudies are hungry for alter. They don't need to spend tall school sitting in course with no ensure that they're really learning, or that what they learn will be important to their lives after graduating. Instep, understudies need a tall

school involvement that plans them for the lives they need to lead. Here are a few key contrasts between the two:

An ability is the capacity to do something, whereas competencies are practices. You learn to clean a window pane as you learn to perform open heart surgery. These are aptitudes. Competencies indicate how the person carries out the aptitudes they have. For illustration, 10 individuals may be gifted at computer programming, but perhaps only five will work in a way that's in line with company culture. This may well be being aware of administration, working proficiently, having great time administration and being a viable group part. Taking a competency-based approach gives teachers adaptability to meet the wants of all understudies, whereas holding all understudies to tall benchmarks of learning. When practiced with constancy, this approach increments value for all learners. In competency-based instruction, teachers create benchmarks and learning objectives for understudies based on the real needs and objectives of their understudy body.

We moreover know that the current demonstrate of tall school does not serve a larger part of understudies. XQ's scene examination of competency-based instruction appears a reality where understudies graduate with transcripts that are a record of time and movement, but not a great degree of the information, abilities, and miens they obtained. Tall school ought to plan understudies with the apparatuses they require for victory within the future. In a competency-based approach, all learning is organized around that objective. Competency-Based Instruction and Value. Conventional tall school frequently takes a "one-size-fits-all" approach to learning: understudies advance based on widespread measures like situate time and scores on standardized tests. In differentiate, competency-based instruction considers each understudy on a person level and inquires: has this understudy aced the abilities and information they require for victory? And on the off chance that not, what learning arrange will engage them to do so?

CONCLUSION

Taking all into consideration, educators should teach with the help of listening and speaking tips in order to improve our listening and speaking skills. Actually, it will be useful with the help of competent based approach. Competency-based instruction or (CBE) is an approach to instruction where studies development through learning substance and aptitudes based on acing a characterized and direct set of center competencies, rather than the time went in course. Organizing by competencies enables instructors to facilitated the guideline of scholastics and center life aptitudes such as collaboration and problem-solving, putting the center on a broader set of comes about and measuring what understudies have truly learned.

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